

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE TRANSLATION TEACHER

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Annotation: *Translation is an academic discipline where the teacher's personality is a crucial factor in achieving the learning goal. Translation should be taught by a person who is an experienced translator, has appropriate professional competence, knows translation activities "from the inside", and is well acquainted with the difficulties, opportunities, and working conditions of a translator.*

Key words: *Task, guidance of the teacher, students, learning materials, textbooks, teaching foreign languages, practical translator, successfully.*

The teacher's own translation experience, the ability to give examples from their own practice, and refer to the experience of their colleagues have a great psychological impact on students, significantly increase their confidence in the teacher's recommendations, and convince them that they really know what they are saying. The teacher's ability to constantly correlate the learning process with practical translation activities, demonstrate how a professional translator would solve a particular translation problem, and convincingly offer their own options increases the effectiveness of teaching. It is important that the translation teacher continues to practice translation, constantly adding to their professional experience. Not every practical translator can successfully teach translation, but every translation teacher should be able to translate professionally. This also provides a comprehensive acquaintance of the teacher with the social status of the profession, market conditions, types of clients, etc.

A translation teacher is also a teacher of the students' native language. When teaching translation, especially translation from a foreign language, a lot of study time is spent discussing options for understanding and translating in your native language. At the same time, it is often found that, having mastered this language since childhood, students do not distinguish well many semantic and stylistic subtleties, do not know how to write literately and elegantly in different styles, and incorrectly assess the appropriateness of using language tools in certain communication situations. It should be borne in mind that if the teacher serves as an unquestionable authority for students in the field of a foreign language, then references to the incorrectness of their native speech usually cause internal resistance and distrust, since students have confidence (often false) that they know their own language as well as others.

The teacher of translation and communication skills must be qualified. In the process of learning, it is constantly necessary to compare the background knowledge of representatives of two language groups, suggest the necessary information to students to understand the content of the original, decide on what cognitive knowledge of receptors they can count on, and what additional information should be included in the translation text itself. One of the most important tasks of training future translators is to expand their background knowledge, bringing them as close as possible to the knowledge of the receptors that the original text is focused on. Translation teaching always has a broad general education function.

The general erudition of the translation teacher is supplemented in the course of training with good, albeit temporary, knowledge in special areas necessary for understanding and translating texts on economics, law, industry, agriculture, science, education, etc. Like a translator, a translation teacher may not be a know-it-all specialist in all fields of activity, but they should be able to acquire and use a minimum of special knowledge in the classroom that makes it possible to solve translation problems that are typical for translating texts of this type.

The main difference between a teacher and a practical translator is that they must not only have the ability to translate freely using all the richness of language tools, but, most importantly, they must be able to explain, show and prove what, how and why to do in order to achieve the desired results. This means that they must be proficient in the language and translation aspects of their course not only practically, but also theoretically, and have a comprehensive knowledge of language theory and translation theory.

The task of the teacher is to teach the student to think "like a translator", to follow the path followed by an experienced professional translator, and for this it is necessary that he should perceive the decisions made as his own, which he came to by inner conviction, although with the help and guidance of the teacher. Keep in mind the following. First, the teacher's critical remarks often cause internal resistance of the student, disagreement, and the desire to justify and defend their own version, which could require a lot of effort, be created in creative torment, and therefore is dear to its author. Secondly, you must be prepared for the fact that, despite all your efforts, you may not be able to immediately convince the student of the unacceptability of the translation option offered to them. Third, you should always keep in mind the variability of the translation, and that, as a rule, several equivalent versions of the translation of the same segment of the original are possible. Therefore, you can't consider a transfer unacceptable just because it doesn't match the option that you think is best. Fourth, you should evaluate the severity of errors and not insist on correcting everything that you would like to improve, given that the choice of some options is a matter of taste and it is the right of each translator to decide what they prefer in each case.

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